

Spectrophotometric Studies on the Composition of Ammonia-Cobalt(II)-Dioxane Complex and its Application in the Estimation of Nitrogen as Kjeldahlised Ammonia

J. P. SINGHAL, SAMIULLAH KHAN AND G. K. GUPTA

Chemical Laboratory, Faculty of Engineering, Muslim University, Aligarh (U.P.)

(Manuscript received 10 May 1972; revised 11 August 1972; accepted 27 September 1972)

Ammonia when allowed to interact with cobalt(II) in presence of dioxane produced a yellowish brown colour in the pH range 5.5-7.5. The colour proved to be sufficiently specific to warrant a close spectrophotometric examination as regards to proper wavelength, reaction ratio, the effect of time and other variables such as concentration of dioxane. The λ_{max} of the complex was found to be 390 nm and the reaction ratio by Job's method of continuous variation as 3 : 2. Results pointed to the possible application of this reaction for the spectrophotometric determination of Kjeldahlised nitrogen in soils and inorganic compounds.

A FEW methods for the determination of nitrogen are known. The most common of these methods is Kjeldahl's procedure¹ where nitrogen is estimated as ammonia. Nessler's Reagent^{2,3,4} is sometimes used for the spectrophotometric determination of ammonia. Phenol hypochlorite^{5,6} reagent is also used. A sensitive, selective and easy method for the determination of Kjeldahlised nitrogen will be of immense importance in the estimation of combined nitrogen in various important materials like soils, fertilizers, explosives and high polymers.

It was noticed in these laboratories that when an aqueous solution of ammonia was treated with an aqueous solution of cobaltous chloride, a green precipitate was produced. This precipitate when dissolved in dioxane yielded a yellowish brown colour. The colour reaction appeared to be sufficiently specific. Therefore it was considered worthwhile to subject it to a close spectrophotometric examination as regards to the nature of the complex formed and the possibility of its application in the spectrophotometric determination of nitrogen as Kjeldahlised ammonia in ammonium salts and soils.

Experimental

Apparatus : The absorbance measurements were made on Bausch and Lomb Spectronic '20' spectrophotometer. Pyrex glassware was used for the preparation of solutions and for carrying out the experiments. pH was measured with Beckman pH meter model G.

Reagents : Standard solutions of cobaltous chloride, ammonia and dioxane were freshly prepared by dissolving requisite weights of pure grade Merck's reagents in double distilled water.

Procedure and Results :

Spectral curves : Absorption spectra were recorded at 30°C and in the pH range 5.5 to 7.5. The method of Vosburgh and Cooper⁷ was employed to ascertain the proper wavelength for carrying out spectrophotometric studies and to determine the number and nature of the complexes present in the colour. 0.005M solutions of cobalt and ammonia were mixed in the ratio 1 : 1, 1 : 2, 2 : 1, 4 : 1, 3 : 1 to 6 ml and to each of these 1.5 ml of 0.025M dioxane was added and the volume made up to 50 ml. Cobaltous chloride solution was used as a blank. The spectra showed a maxima at 390 nm (see Fig. 1, curves 1 to 4)

Fig. 1

in all cases, indicating that it was the most suitable wavelength for further spectrophotometric work. The results also pointed to the formation of only one complex in the above reaction.

Standard curve : A standard curve was drawn by distilling 0.02 g of NH_4Cl with 100 cc of 50% NaOH using Kjeldahl assembly and collecting the distillate in 25 ml of 0.1M Co(II) solution. Colour was then developed by adding 1.5 ml of 0.025M dioxane to various concentrations of the complex solution,

absorbance taken and a standard curve drawn. Beer Lambert Law was followed from 0 to 280 ppm of nitrogen by the above distillate mixture in the pH range of 5.5 to 7.5.

Effect of dioxane concentration: Concentration of dioxane was found to affect the colour intensity. Best results were obtained on adding 180 ppm of dioxane to the complex solution.

Full colour development occurred in about 30 min. The colour was stable for nearly 3 hrs. Thereafter precipitation occurred especially in the range of high concentration.

Determination of reaction ratio: Job's method of continuous variation^{8,9} was used to determine the composition of complex formed in the solution. For this purpose equimolar concentration of ammonia and cobaltous chloride were mixed and the requisite amount of dioxane added. The sum of the concentration of ammonia and cobalt(II) was kept constant viz., $2.5 \times 10^{-4}M$, $2.0 \times 10^{-4}M$ and $1.66 \times 10^{-4}M$ respectively, while their ratio varied (see Fig. 2,

Fig. 2

curves a, b and c). A plot of absorbance against mole ratio of ammonia for measurement at 390 nm gave maxima at a mole ratio of 0.6 in all cases pointing to the presence of a 3 : 2 complex of ammonia and cobalt, i.e.,

Determination of nitrogen as Kjeldahlised ammonia in ammonium salts: 0.02 g of each of NH_4Cl and $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ were distilled with 100 ml of 50% NaOH in Kjeldahl flasks and nitrogen estimated as ammonia with the help of the standard curve using cobaltous chloride and dioxane as colour reagents.

Nitrogen in soils: 1 g of soil, 10 g K_2SO_4 , 0.5 g $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$, a few pieces of porcelain and 25 ml of conc. H_2SO_4 were taken in a Kjeldahl flask and shaken till the contents were well mixed. The mixture was digested till it became colourless (usually for 90–120 min). The flask was then cooled and 100 ml of water added. The mixture was distilled with 100 ml of 50% NaOH and a few fragments of granulated zinc. The distillate was collected in 25 ml of 0.1M

$\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ solution and the volume made to 500 ml. 5 ml of this solution was taken in a 50 ml flask and colour developed with 1.5 ml of 0.025M dioxane. After 30 min. measurements were made on Bausch and Lomb spectronic "20" and the amount of nitrogen in soils calculated. Nitrogen was also determined as per usual Kjeldahl procedure. The results for amount of nitrogen obtained by the recommended method are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1. PERCENTAGE OF NITROGEN AS ESTIMATED BY DIFFERENT METHODS

Material used	Cobalt(II) dioxane method	Acid method	Theoretical value
NH_4Cl	24.76	24.62	24.34
$(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$	21.35	21.11	21.20
Soil Type 3	0.30	0.29	—
Soil Type 5	0.23	0.22	—

Discussion

An examination of the data obtained during the above investigations pointed to the definite possibility of the application of the colour reaction between ammonia, cobaltous chloride and dioxane for the detection and spectrophotometric estimation of Kjeldahlised ammonia in soils and in inorganic compounds. It is clear from table 1 that the results obtained by this method are almost of the same accuracy as the previous methods and can be successfully used for the determination of nitrogen in the case of soils and inorganic compounds. In the case of organic compounds, this method, however, failed to give satisfactory results.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Dr. N. C. Saha and Dr. Mohsin Qureshi for providing research facilities.

References

1. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text-Book of Quantitative Analysis", 3rd ed., Longman Green & Co. Ltd., London.
2. H. F. BEEGHLY, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1942, **14**, 137–40.
3. M. MARZADRO, *Ann. Chim. applicata*, 1945, **35**, 231–5.
4. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", Interscience Publishers, New York, 1959.
5. D. D. VAN SIKYE and A. HILLER, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1933, **102**, 499–504.
6. J. A. RUSSELL, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1944, **156**, 457–61.
7. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 1630.
8. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, **9**, 13.
9. W. C. VOSBURGH and G. R. COOPER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.